

Tactics of orthodontic treatment of children and methods for the prevention of caries

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Abstract:

For the prevention and treatment of lesions of hard tooth tissues, a method of deep fluorination with tifenfluorides was proposed, which for a long time emit fluorine in high concentration, contributing to reliable remineralization.

Currently, many fundamental aspects of prevention in the process of orthodontic treatment have not yet been fully resolved. There is no data on the use of the deep fluorination method in orthodontics. The issues of assessing the resistance of tooth enamel and the effectiveness of remineralizing agents with the help of mouthguards in the process of orthodontic treatment are not adequately covered. In this regard, the urgent task is the further development of preventive measures in the process of orthodontic treatment.

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Introduction

Taking into account the pronounced relationship between the development of dental caries and periodontal diseases on the hygienic state of the oral cavity, before orthodontic treatment, the level of hygienic knowledge and skills was determined in all patients by questioning and assessing manual skills. Analysis of the data obtained indicated a low level of knowledge on the prevention of dental diseases and the acquisition of manual skills.

An assessment of manual oral care skills showed that only 10.4% of children demonstrated correct brushing, which was rated as good. Satisfactory manual skills in oral care were found in 19%, unsatisfactory - in 69.7% of children with orthodontic treatment.

Main part

Given the low baseline level of awareness of children and adolescents on oral hygiene and the high percentage of unsatisfactory manual skills, there was a need for prolonged training, motivational education and monthly monitoring at all stages of orthodontic treatment. Taking into account the direct relationship between oral hygiene and the development of dental caries and periodontal tissue diseases, it should be noted that dental educational work, professional oral hygiene, in the process of which not only teaching technique takes place, observing the time and frequency of brushing teeth, but also manual skills with the criterion of self-control in the form of a feeling of smoothness of the teeth and the surface of the orthodontic apparatus is an essential element of the complex of preventive measures.

At the initial examination, professional hygiene was carried out with the selection of individual means and methods of oral hygiene and a set of therapeutic and preventive measures was prescribed:

Carrying out endogenous drug-free prophylaxis by reducing the frequency of consumption of carbohydrates, if possible, exclude their use between meals, fixing the habit of rinsing the mouth with water after each meal. It is necessary to increase the self-cleaning of the oral cavity by eating grated fruits and vegetables, which contribute to abundant salivation, which reduces the viscosity of saliva and flushes food debris from the mouth.

Consumption of solid foods - cookies, caramel, chips, ice cream and fizzy drinks is strictly prohibited. It is recommended to eat food rich in micro and macro elements, vitamins, amino acids and proteins.

Implementation of exogenous prophylaxis through the implementation of professional oral hygiene and training in individual hygiene procedures during 3 planned visits before the installation of orthodontic equipment and every 3 months during orthodontic

The introduction of the gel R.O.C.S. Medical Minerals (R.O.C.S.) in the mouthguard for further application

The product can be used constantly, as it is harmless, which is especially important for patients who have been on orthodontic treatment for a long time.

Conclusions

Thus, the approaches to the selection of events were individualized, taking into account the prognosis, and the CVL complex was adapted to the specificity of the intensity, structure and severity of dental diseases in patients treated with NOT and COT.

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